

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Some Cyclic Ketones by Selenium Dioxide

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The kinetics of the oxidation of cyclohexanone, cycloheptanone and cyclooctanone by selenium dioxide in 50% (v/v) acetic acid water mixtures has been reported. A first order dependence in each selenium dioxide and ketone have been observed. The rate of the oxidation reaction has been found to be accelerated by the increase in the mineral acid concentrations. The effects of solvent, solvent isotope, temperature, etc. on the rate of oxidation have been studied in detail to determine bimolecular oxidation. The values of energy of activation, the entropy of activation and frequency factor for the reaction have been evaluated.

SELENIUM DIOXIDE has been used as a potent oxidant in organic reactions, by a large number of workers¹⁻⁶. It has been also used extensively in the kinetic studies of the oxidations of several organic compounds⁷⁻¹¹ including that of ketones. The present communication presents the kinetics and mechanism of cyclohexanone, cycloheptanone and cyclooctanone by selenium dioxide for the first time.

Experimental

Stock solution (0.1M) of selenium dioxide was prepared by dissolving its B.D.H. sample in redistilled water. The solution was standardised at equal intervals iodometrically. Glacial acetic acid solution was distilled over Cr_2O_3 to remove any reducing impurity present. 2M solution each of cyclohexanone, cycloheptanone and cyclooctanone was prepared in glacial acetic acid. The volume of glacial acetic acid required for each standard solution was carefully calculated.

Analytical grade inorganic and organic chemicals were used throughout the investigations, Deuterium oxide was supplied by Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay with a stated deuterium content of 99.4%.

Kinetic Measurements :

The kinetic experiments were carried out at constant temperature ($\pm 0.05^\circ$). The solvent used was 50% acetic acid (v/v). The reaction flask containing oxidant, acetic acid and other reagents was kept in the thermostat together with a stock solution of ketone. When the two flasks attained the temperature of thermostat, a required volume of ketone solution was drawn out and poured into reaction flask. Zero time was taken at the instance when half of the solution was in the reaction flask.

Immediately a 2 mls aliquot was withdrawn into a ice cooled flask containing 10 mls of 0.01N thio-sulphate solution along with 5 mls of 4 N HCl. 2 mls of freshly prepared starch solution were then added. The unreacted thiosulphate was titrated against 0.05N iodine solution till a blue colour developed. The titre value gave the amount of excess of thiosulphate left. Aliquots were withdrawn at known intervals of time. The titre values for 10 mls of 0.01N thiosulphate was designated as T. If the titre value at zero time be T_0 then the initial amount of $\text{SeO}_2 = T - T_0 = a$, amount at any instant ' t ' = $T - T_t = (a - x)$.

Fairly good first order rate constants were calculated from the integrated first order equation :

$$k_1 = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{a}{(a-x)}$$

Stoichiometry :

Reaction mixtures containing excess of selenium dioxide (about 20 times) over ketone were allowed to equilibrate at 60° in sulphuric acid of suitable concentration. The results showed that one mole of ketone required one mole of selenium dioxide for complete oxidation. In the oxidation of cycloheptanone 1 : 2 cycloheptane dione was isolated. The stoichiometric equation for which may be represented as :

Results

When the concentration of ketone and hydrogen ion are kept high compared to the oxidant, the

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TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE ON RATE OF REAGENTS CONCENTRATIONS

Solvent=50% HoAc (V/V), Temperature=60°

$10^3 \times [\text{SeO}_2]$ M	$10^3 \times [\text{Ketone}]$ M	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$			$k_2 \times 10^3$ l mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹		
		Cyclohexa- none	Cyclohepta- none	Cycloocta- none	Cyclohexa- none	Cyclohepta- none	Cycloocta- none
4.0	10.0	2.0380	4.834	9.831	203.8	48.34	98.31
6.0	10.0	2.0290	4.896	9.539	202.90	48.96	95.39
8.0	10.0	2.0420	4.912	9.166	204.20	49.12	91.66
10.0	10.0	2.0320	4.846	9.438	203.20	48.46	94.38
6.0	14.0	1.6760	6.867	13.110	200.10	49.02	93.63
6.0	12.0	1.3510	5.896	11.610	178.80	49.11	96.78
6.0	8.0	0.9484	3.926	7.428	173.00	49.07	92.85
6.0	6.0	0.6798	2.904	6.034	170.70	48.40	100.57
6.0	4.0	0.4924	1.913	3.894	201.00	48.82	97.35

rate at which the oxidant disappears follows the first order rate law. The kinetics of oxidation of cyclohexanone, cycloheptanone, and cyclooctanone by selenium dioxide was performed at several initial concentrations of reactants (Table 1). The results show the reaction to be first order both in oxidant

and ketone at constant H⁺ ion and solvent composition. The second order rate constant $k_2 = k_1/[\text{ketone}]$ for cyclic ketones were calculated (Table 1). The slopes of the plots of $\log k_1$ vs log ketone were found to be approximately unity which confirm a first order dependence in ketone concentration.

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [H^+]$

—□—Cycloheptanone
—△—Cyclooctanone
—○—Cyclohexanone

H⁺ Ion Dependence :

Runs were carried out by varying the hydrogen ion concentration keeping the temperature, reactant concentrations and solvent concentration constant. The range investigated was 0.5 to 4.0 M H₂SO₄ at 30° (Table 2). The rate constants were calculated by usual procedure. The slope of the plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [H^+]$ were found to be approximately unity establishing first order dependence in [H⁺] ions.

Influence of Solvent :

The reaction was studied in various acetic acid water binary mixtures (20-70%). Increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the reaction mixture increases the rate of oxidation. The plots (Fig. 2) of $\log k$ vs reciprocal of dielectric constant 'D' are linear with positive slopes which show that the slow stage involves a neutral molecule-positive ion reaction.

TABLE 2—ACID DEPENDENCE ON REACTION RATE

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ M	$[\text{SeO}_2] \times 10^3 = 6.0M$ Solvent=50% HoAc (v/v)			$1 + \log [\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$	Ketone=0.0 × 10 ⁻¹ M Temperature=30°C		
	$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$				$4 + \log k_1$		
	Cyclohe- xanone	Cyclohep- tanone	Cycloocta- none		Cyclohexa- none	Cyclohepta- none	Cycloocta- none
0.50	4.216	6.507	—	0.6990	1.6280	0.8134	—
0.75	—	9.657	—	—	—	0.9850	—
1.00	7.614	12.170	2.444	1.0000	1.8816	1.0858	1.3881
1.50	11.320	18.360	3.391	1.1761	2.0542	1.2639	1.5303
2.00	13.620	22.630	3.917	1.3010	2.1342	1.3547	1.5930
3.00	20.630	33.630	5.792	1.4771	2.3145	1.5267	1.7628
4.00	25.630	41.260	6.845	1.6021	2.4086	1.6155	1.8554

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log k_1$ vs Reciprocal of dielectric constant

—□—Cycloheptanone
—△—Cyclooctanone
—○—Cyclohexanone

Effect of Temperature :

Kinetic runs were carried out for the three ketones in a temperature range of 30° . The plots of $1/T$ vs $\log k_2$ resulted in a straight lines (Figure not given). Arrhenius parameters were calculated from the slopes of the graphs. The values of energy of activation, frequency factor and entropy of activations are given in Table 3.

Solvent Isotope Effect :

Deuterium oxide was used in place of water to study its effect on the oxidation reaction. Due to the mass difference between hydrogen and deuterium the reaction rates should be differently effected. A change over from water to 70% deuterium oxide increases the rates of oxidation of cyclic ketones (Table 4). This also confirms the attack of the reacting species of the oxidant on the keto form of cyclic ketones.

Discussion

The rates of enolisation of ketones are usually measured by reactions such as halogenation¹², racemisation¹³ and deuteration¹⁴. All these processes occur by zero order dependence. In the present case the rate is first order in SeO_3 and hence rate determining enolisation as a mechanism is ruled out. Schaefer and Corey¹⁵ have also ruled out such a slow stage in the oxidation of deoxybenzoin.

The various species of SeO_3 which may exist in aqueous acetic acid mixtures are (I) monoprotonated species HSeO_3^+ , (II) hydrated oxide species H_2SeO_3 , (III) hydrated and protonated H_3SeO_3^+ species, (IV) acetylated species AcHSeO_3 and (V) acetylated and protonated species $\text{AcH}_2\text{SeO}_3^+$. The unhydrated oxide SeO_3 cannot exist in aqueous solution. The protonated species HSeO_3^+ is stronger electrophile compared to H_2SeO_3 , but may not exist in aqueous solutions. The mechanism of oxidation is thus to be considered in terms of oxidant species (II) or (V).

On the basis of the observed experimental results it may be considered that in solvents containing large percentage of acetic acid, selenius acid may exist as acetylated species of selenius acid. This is supported by the results of Melnikov et al⁴ who have reported the isolation of Se(IV) esters of alcohols.

In acid medium, the acid conjugate of selenium (IV) ester is expected to be a more potent oxidant. Thus the oxidant species $\text{RH}_2\text{SeO}_3^+$ in acidic medium in presence of 50% acetic acid is considered to react with cyclohexanone forming an intermediate product(X).

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS
Solvent=50% HoAc (v/v)

ΔE K cal mole ⁻¹			PZ(A) l mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹			$\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.		
Cyclohexa- none	Cyclohepta- none	Cycloocta- none	Cyclohexa- none	Cyclohepta- none	Cycloocta- none	Cyclohexa- none	Cyclohepta- none	Cycloocta- none
10.60	17.7	16.9	1.596×10^9	1.928×10^{10}	1.096×10^{10}	-39.90	-21.76	-22.79

TABLE 4—SOLVENT ISOTOPE EFFECT

[Ketone]= $10 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]=0.028 M$, AcOH=20% (v/v), $[\text{SeO}_3]=6 \times 10^{-3} M$

$K_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$			$K_{\text{D}_2\text{O}} \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$			$K_{\text{D}_2\text{O}}/K_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$		
Cyclohexa- none	Cyclohepta- none	Cycloocta- none	Cyclohexa- none	Cyclohepta- none	Cycloocta- none	Cyclohexa- none	Cyclohepta- none	Cycloocta- none
1.447	4.143	7.161	3.667	11.23	19.67	2.533	2.711	2.748

This intermediate (X) is considered to be the enol ester of cyclohexanone which after rearrangement rapidly decomposes into products.

Lauer et al¹⁶ have studied the oxidation of olefins by SeO₂ and have reported the similar type of formation of Se(II) esters and their subsequent decomposition in the temperature range, 70°-100°.

The mechanism of the oxidation of cyclohexanone by SeO₂ in acid medium may, therefore, be given as follows :

On the basis of the experimental results the acid catalysed oxidation of cyclic ketones may be formulated by taking the specific example of cyclohexanone as :

(1) Concerted attack of nucleophile (H₂O) and electrophile RH₂SeO₃⁺ on cyclohexanone to give Se(IV) ester (X)

(2) Conversion of enol Se(IV) ester(X) into the enol Se(II) ester (Y) by an internal rearrangement

(3) Acid catalysed 1, 2 elimination from (Y) to give the oxidation products

The observed reactivity of the cyclic ketones studied is in the following order

Cyclohexanone > Cyclooctanone > Cycloheptanone

This may be due to the conformational influences of the ketones. The higher reactivity of cyclohexanone is probably due to the terminal hydrogen of nearly strainless puckered residue (CH₂)₄ in cyclohexanone fulfilling the stereochemical requirements for hyperconjugation with the cyclic C=C group.¹⁷

It is generally presumed that the most favoured conformation of cycloheptanone¹⁸ is the twist chair form which is responsible for the lowest rate observed in the oxidation process. The difference in reactivity between cyclooctanone and cycloheptanone is due to the existence of former in the crown form and latter in the chair form.

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